

An Unusual Cause of Recurrent Upper Gastrointestinal Bleeding: Duodenal Varices in Portal Hypertension

Zineb Boukhal, Manar Fartmissi ✉, Fatima Zahra El Rhaoussi, Mohamed Tahiri, Fouad Haddad, Wafaa Hliwa, Ahmed Bellabah, Wafaa Badre
Department of Gastroenterology and Hepatology, Ibn Rochd University Hospital, Center, Casablanca, Morocco

Abstract

Duodenal varices are an uncommon cause of upper gastrointestinal bleeding in patients with portal hypertension and may be overlooked during endoscopic evaluation. We report the case of a 44-year-old woman with portal hypertension secondary to alcohol-related chronic liver disease who presented with recurrent upper gastrointestinal bleeding manifested by hematemesis and melena. Emergency upper gastrointestinal endoscopy revealed three duodenal varices located in the duodenal bulb, one of which showed an adherent platelet-fibrin clot with active bleeding, while only a small gastroesophageal varix without high-risk stigmata was observed on retroflexion. Endoscopic band ligation of the bleeding duodenal varix was successfully performed, achieving immediate hemostasis without complications. The patient remained clinically stable with no recurrence of bleeding and was discharged on secondary prophylaxis. This case highlights duodenal varices as a rare but potentially life-threatening source of gastrointestinal bleeding and emphasizes the importance of careful endoscopic examination in patients with portal hypertension.

Introduction

Portal hypertension is a progressive complication of liver cirrhosis and leads to the formation of portosystemic collaterals, typically at the esophagogastric junction, rectum, and abdominal wall [1]. When these collaterals develop outside the esophagogastric region, they are termed ectopic varices (EcV) [1,2]. Although rare, ectopic varices account for 2-5% of all variceal bleeding and can be associated with a high mortality rate of up to 40% [3]. Duodenal varices (DV) represent approximately 17% of ectopic varices and are predominantly located in the duodenal bulb and second portion of the duodenum [4]. They are infrequently encountered, with a reported prevalence of 0.2-0.4% in patients undergoing upper gastrointestinal endoscopy [5]. Duodenal varices typically arise in the context of portal hypertension though they can also result from trauma, tumors, vascular anomalies, or thrombotic disorders [6]. Despite their rarity, ectopic varices have a higher risk of bleeding compared to gastroesophageal varices, and hemorrhage from duodenal varices represents a life-

threatening complication. There is currently no standardized treatment approach for duodenal variceal bleeding due to the limited number of cases reported. Available management strategies include endoscopic interventions (band ligation or sclerotherapy with glue injection), interventional radiological embolization, pharmacologic therapy, and surgery [7].

We present a case of massive upper gastrointestinal bleeding secondary to duodenal varices in a patient with decompensated alcoholic liver illustrating the diagnostic and therapeutic challenges posed by this rare but serious condition.

Case Presentation

A 44-year-old woman presented to the emergency department with hematemesis and melena associated with poorly tolerated anemia. She had a long history of chronic alcohol consumption for 20 years and had been abstinent for one year. Her medical history was notable for chronic arthralgia treated with corticosteroids. Four months earlier, she had been hospitalized for upper gastrointestinal bleeding secondary to esophageal varices treated with endoscopic band ligation and was

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subsequently placed on non-selective beta-blocker therapy. On admission, she appeared pale and mildly jaundiced, with hypotension. Abdominal examination revealed mild tenderness without signs of peritonitis, and rectal examination confirmed melena. Laboratory

tests demonstrated severe anemia, thrombocytopenia, prolonged prothrombin time, hyperbilirubinemia, hypoalbuminemia, and preserved renal function (Table 1).

Table 1: The Initial Labs Result

Test	Result	Unit	Reference Range
Hemoglobin	3.8	g/dL	12–16
Platelets	133	10 ⁹ /L	150-400
Albumin	27	g/L	35-50
Total bilirubin	4.5	mg/L	0.2-1.2
Aspartate aminotransferase	36	IU/L	<35
Alanine aminotransferase	13	IU/L	<35
Creatinine	0.47	mg/dL	0.6–1.2
Blood nitrogen urea	35	35 mg/dL	7-20
Prothrombin time	44	%	70-100
Factor V	51	%	70-100
Hepatitis B surface antigen	Negative	-	-
Hepatitis C anti-body	Negative	-	-

The patient received urgent resuscitation with intravenous fluids and transfusion of five units of packed red blood cells. Following hemodynamic stabilization, medical therapy for acute variceal bleeding was initiated, including intravenous octreotide administered as a 50 µg bolus followed by a continuous infusion at 50 µg/hour, intravenous ceftriaxone at a dose of 1 g once daily for infection prophylaxis, and oral lactulose syrup administered

three times daily for prevention of hepatic encephalopathy.

After initial resuscitation, emergency upper gastrointestinal endoscopy was performed. Retroflexion revealed a small gastroesophageal varix without red signs. In the duodenal bulb, three ectopic duodenal varices were identified, one of which exhibited an adherent platelet-fibrin clot with active oozing (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Endoscopic View of a Duodenal Varix Located in the Duodenal Bulb, Showing an Adherent Platelet-Fibrin Clot Consistent with Recent or Active Bleeding

Endoscopic band ligation was successfully applied to the bleeding varix, resulting in immediate hemostasis without complications. The patient remained hemodynamically stable with no recurrence of bleeding during hospitalization and was discharged on

secondary prophylaxis. Based on clinical and laboratory findings, she was classified as Child-Pugh class B.

Discussion

Bleeding from duodenal varices (DV) is a rare but serious complication of portal hypertension, first

described by Alberti et al. in 1931 [8]. Although its exact prevalence is difficult to determine due to diagnostic challenges, angiographic studies have revealed duodenal varices in up to 40% of patients with portal hypertension [4]. The most frequent underlying cause remains liver cirrhosis, accounting for approximately 30% of cases, followed by splenic and portal vein obstructions secondary to pancreatitis, malignancy, or thrombosis [7].

Clinically, bleeding from duodenal varices may present with hematemesis, melena, or even hematochezia [8]. In patients with portal hypertension and no evidence of active bleeding from esophageal or gastric varices, duodenal varices should be considered as a potential source, particularly if melena is present without hematemesis. The mortality rate associated with DV bleeding can be high-up to 40%-largely due to the difficulty in prompt diagnosis and the severity of hemorrhage [9].

Anatomically, duodenal varices most commonly develop in the duodenal bulb but can occur throughout the duodenum. Their deep location in the serosal layer, unlike esophageal varices that lie in the submucosa, contributes to the diagnostic challenge. The formation of duodenal varices is driven by increased portal pressure leading to portosystemic shunts through veins such as the pancreaticoduodenal and gastroduodenal veins [10]. Geographical differences in presentation have also been observed. In Western populations, duodenal varices are more often located in the bulb and associated with extra-hepatic portal vein obstruction, whereas in Asian countries, the descending portion of the duodenum is more commonly affected, with cirrhosis being the leading etiology [4,9,11].

Endoscopy remains the primary diagnostic tool, though lesions-particularly small or distally located varices-can be easily missed. Given the complexity of these cases, current guidelines from the American Association for the Study of Liver Diseases (AASLD) emphasize a multidisciplinary approach involving hepatologists, endoscopists, interventional radiologists, and surgeons [12].

In terms of management, the initial priority is hemodynamic stabilization with appropriate resuscitation. Medical therapy may help stabilize the patient, but definitive control of bleeding typically requires endoscopic, radiologic, or surgical intervention. While surgery-including variceal ligation, duodenal resection, and shunt procedures-was historically a mainstay of treatment, these approaches are now reserved for refractory cases due to their high morbidity and mortality rates [13].

Over the past two decades, endoscopic therapies have become central to the management of bleeding duodenal varices. Endoscopic band ligation (EBL), in

particular, has been increasingly reported as an effective and safe option. In our case, EBL was performed successfully, leading to immediate hemostasis without complication. Shiraishi et al. reported achieving hemostasis using band ligation alone [14]. Similar outcomes have been described in other case reports, with some requiring adjunctive or rescue therapies such as cyanoacrylate injection or transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt (TIPS) in the event of rebleeding [15].

In cases where endoscopic management is unsuccessful or technically unfeasible, interventional radiology provides additional options. TIPS can reduce portal pressure and is often considered in patients with recurrent bleeding or as a bridge to liver transplantation [16].

BRTO (balloon-occluded retrograde transvenous obliteration) has been less frequently reported in patients with DV, but case reports and small case series have shown successful treatment with this modality. A systematic review that included 21 patients undergoing BRTO for bleeding DV showed excellent technical results with only 2 patients suffering early re-bleed [17].

Surgery remains a last-resort strategy when less invasive measures fail or when the varix is anatomically inaccessible. While surgical duodenectomy or shunt placement has shown success in selected cases, these procedures carry significant perioperative risk and should be carefully considered [13].

Conclusions

In summary, due to the rarity of duodenal varices and the absence of large-scale studies, treatment remains individualized. Our case supports the growing evidence that endoscopic band ligation can be a first-line, effective approach to bleeding duodenal varices. Further studies and multicenter registries are needed to better establish guidelines and comparative efficacy among available treatment modalities

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